

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** SIKUBWABO**FIRST NAME:** Jean Marie Vianney**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show essential information below:**The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2016 on Windows 10

[Plagiarism rate: 1%](#)**Deleted:** .**List your seven key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your R.P.) (samples below):**

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-14)
3. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)
5. Chicago Manual of Style Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2021, 44-55)
6. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 56-61)
7. Some inconsistencies in the material (EUCLID 2021, ii, 5,12)

Commented [GK1]: The citation in the list of key concepts and that in the body of the paper are different. Note that you cannot cite a single source differently in the same paper. Kindly make the citations uniform- use either EUCLID 2021 or Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021!**Deleted:** : plagiarism rate: 1%

GETTING PREPARED FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

My professional preoccupations include writing consultancy proposals, presentations, and reports. In these activities, I inevitably needed to apply different writing techniques, and more specifically, I could not figure out what errors I might have made in my documents. Since EUCLID aims to promote high-quality scientific works, and in a bid to prevent students at EUCLID start writing their papers from scratch, it had availed an instructional material that guides the students on how to write effectively and efficiently at the early beginning of their academic programs. Against that background, the ACA-401D period one (1) course contains the materials of coursepack designated for students to prepare for academic essay writing. A 14-minute instructional video details the rules of writing, practical instructions for writing Response Papers, and generally, how to manipulate the document. That video supplements the materials of this coursepack. Separately to this instructional video, two videos (a guide to Grammarly use and a guide to Zotero use) give detailed instructions on using these applications to meet the required academic writing standards at EUCLID.

In this present response paper, I will conduct a detailed reflection on the following concepts from the coursepack, namely: the basics of essay writing, avoiding plagiarism in academic writing, some rules of thumb for writing papers, American vs. British English, Chicago Manual Style Crib Sheet, as well as Latin expressions and abbreviation. The present course provides solutions to my academic writing challenges and will improve my professional performance.

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2) FROM CONCEPT TO EVIDENCE PRODUCTION IN ESSAY WRITING

Chapter one (1) of the ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack is related to the basics of essay writing. As emphasized by the University of New South Wales (UNSW), an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 1), answer a question that pushed the writer to choose the topic, while the answer should be evidence-based discussions, and arguments. This chapter outlines the steps of essay writing and how to go about each step. In this chapter, I learned that the starting point for an essay is the writer's initial response to the topic or question and the importance of questioning the writer's response. Like any other project, writing a thesis is a project that requires enough time, which means that it cannot be an activity of a single study session (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). My take-home from this point is that I must start writing what I know from a sentence to a paragraph and then the passage. In so doing, I must have a clear plan with issues to address, make plausible responses that will guide me in my research, and finally, organize my ideas, as well as the proper structure of the essay. Because the writer's materials are a foundation of evidence, I learned from this chapter that every resource is not worth reading; I must read functional materials to answer the essay questions. It does not allow me to stay in the essay's context only and save on time.

Though this course and many other materials teach the steps and techniques for planning, searching, and writing essays, it had reserved for researchers to be creative and critical thinkers, which helps them make reasoned decisions about each information used in the report. Additionally, this course taught me how to manage stress in essay writing by avoiding panic though there might be faults in the essay because that is part of the essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 4). In light of that, I learned that I must remain calm, think further, collect information, and analyze data in a more challenging way. This chapter changed my writing habits because I do not have to include only evidence agreeing with what I am arguing. Instead, I learned that I must consider other constructive criticisms, challenging arguments, and opposing views because they help us think more profoundly and have objective discussions of the topic.

3) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM IN ACADEMIC WRITINGS

According to EUCLID, plagiarism is when the writer uses a resource of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information. It consists of taking

someone's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not crediting the author (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5). Kate L. Turabian emphasizes that researchers risk being charged with plagiarism even if they were not intentionally dishonest but only misinformed or careless (Turabian et al. 2013, 80).

Because the resources enrich the writer's ideas, they consult. In contrast, the writer must cite every source of information they included in the work; I was apprehensive about overciting the sources of information. With this coursepack, I learned that to avoid overciting, the writer must paraphrase ideas differently from how the author initially wrote the information while not changing or rearranging the structure of the sentence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7).

When writing an essay, references do not guard the writer against plagiarism but are also a way to recognize and credit the author for the effort and time invested in the work (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5). This chapter on plagiarism describes all the rules and techniques of citing the sources of information and some exceptions to these rules (for example, when the information is well known or common sense). According to EUCLID, the writer can know if they write about common knowledge. If it is repeated in many sources that [you have read], you can assume it is common knowledge (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10). I understand that the writer must remain cautious against plagiarism in my writings. However, I am still not entirely convinced that if many different sources have repeated the same information, it makes it common knowledge because it depends on the topic or issue under discussion. The leading example is the current Covid-19 pandemic, prevention of its spread, and vaccination of two-three dozens that have become hitting talks in different fields (e.g., media, political, academic, and health-related). The impact of COVID-19 on political, socio-economic development and the vaccines' effectiveness are the current great debates and arguments in different writings. Does this make it common knowledge and prevent the writer from citing the sources about the effectiveness of the two-three dozens vaccine?

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4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

In my daily professional activities, I write proposals, slides for presentations, and reports for the attention of the audience or readers. Though the listeners and readers do not give feedback about the writing style, format, or grammar, their proper use adds value to the written document. It enables the writer to deliver the message they intended to provide. In this regard, chapter three of the present coursepack elaborates the rules to follow when writing any paper to remain on track of the topic under discussion, help the readers to receive important messages/information from the document, be objective and professional in their argumentation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14). This coursepack alerted me that misplacement of words, lack of proper words, even simple functions can completely change the context or confuse the reader. Therefore, since the writer aims to deliver specific information to the readers, I learned from this course that I must use clear and understandable language instead of very complicated or archaic words.

Because the writing typically attracts the reader's attention to the writer's idea, the writer should organize messages well so that each statement flows smoothly. To that end, the writer should not use very long sentences and paragraphs as they do not allow the reader to focus on the information they read though very short sentences or paragraphs are also a distraction (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 15). Writing also consists of arguments in line with the topic or issue under discussion, while the writer refers to previous papers related to the topic. However, I learned that I should not criticize for charging or disagreeing for the sake of disagreeing. Instead, I must argue against myself and ask myself how the philosopher would respond to my criticism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16); in that way, I will make objective and constructive criticism. For that reason, given that there might be other writings that criticize the philosopher's writing, I must make a comparative analysis and draw my point of view from that analysis.

5) USE OF AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter six (6) of this coursepack elaborates on fundamental differences between American and British English and their change influences. The chapter discusses American political, economic, technological, and cultural forces worldwide, especially English use (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 27). Both American and British English have respective writing rules, punctuation, the spelling of words, and grammatical rules, whose misuse can alter the passage's context.

Like many other Rwandans, it has already been a decade while I transited from French to English. In my writings, I have a tendency that the English spoken in a country is mostly the same worldwide. I have been using English and British words interchangeably (e.g., endeavor vs. endeavour, recognize vs. recognise, people vs. persons, Etc.) without paying much attention to some variations they have, yet these variations can cause misunderstanding of the message. Often, I have been using informal English expressions, contractions, black English depending on the categories of people I have been interacting with, without bearing in mind the influence of this usage on the quality of the writing. This coursepack warned me to be vigilant about each of the two English rules. Apart from spelling words, pronunciation, punctuations, writing dates, and numbers, Standard American English and Standard British English have different grammatical rules and pluralize words and adjectives. However, the SBE still raises questions about pluralizing large collective nouns (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 30). Referring to two examples below taken from the coursepack, I see that the SBE had not detailed the rules related to the plural of large collective nouns, yet the subject is singular:

Finnair **has** a flight to London today (U.S.) vs. Finnair **have** a flight to London today (G.B.)
England **has** (...) played well today, even if **it** lost (U.S.) vs. England **have** (...) played well today even if **they** lost (G.B.)

From these examples, I still raise the need to detail specific rules and formulas on the use of the plural for large collective nouns because the subject or word before the verb is singular because the grammatical rule is that the verb must match with the subject of the

sentence. However, the general view is that the SBE uses the plural for large collective nouns if they refer to a group of individuals; for example, football players have played well.

6) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE CRIB SHEET

Chapter eight (8) analyzes the Chicago style described by Dr. Abel Scribe, which is the style of formatting books and research papers. It is documented in version 2003 of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, Dissertations documents, the formatting books, and research papers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 44). Before starting this coursepack, I was not fully knowledgeable about abbreviations, italic words, proper quotations, and I could unknowingly cause the readers to lose their focus on the document.

In my writing habits, I have been using acronyms and abbreviations such as *e.g.*, *i.e.*, *etc.*, in the text as part of the sentence and explaining them in the list of acronyms and abbreviations. The risk of this writing habit was the difficulties to the readers as they were required to go back to the list of acronyms and abbreviations to check their meaning, resulting in loss of focus in the document. On the contrary, as instructed by this coursepack, I learned that once I opt for using these acronyms and abbreviations, I must use them in parenthetical comments injected into the text (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 44). However, these rules accept the use of the acronym "U.S." or "U.S." as an adjective in running text instead of a noun (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 45). Surprisingly, the rules do not specify any motivation around this exception.

The same rules apply for compound words, two or more words that work together in a specific order. These include full-time compound words, conditional compound words, and prefixes. Despite some exceptions, the general rule is that these compound words must be hyphenated, whatever their role in a sentence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 46). In my writings, I used to hyphen some commonly used prefixes such as reexamine, cofounder, and so on, without paying any attention to the specific exceptions of hyphening words of the same letters, superlatives, or diminutives, or when I want to improve the clarity of the expression. From now on, I will take this material as my diary that will be guiding me in my writing should any difficulty or confusion persist as for application of the general rules or exceptions for the hyphenated words.

When watching the video "basic ACA-401 tutorial," Prof. Cleenewerck emphasized using American Psychological Association (APA) and Chicago Manual Style (CMS) in writing. The introductory video taught me that the APA style mainly applies to social sciences such as sociology, psychology, medicine, or social work. On another side, CMS is primarily used in humanities; I remained curious about how they are used practically differently despite their similar writing requirements. With this coursepack, I learned that the CMS was detailed in a manual reserved for students and researchers in the form of Turabian, which is the most recent development of CMS. The writing structure plays a vital role at the EUCLID, and noticing that the coursepack highly recommends using the Turabian (in-text parenthetical) in citing sources. Therefore, I must pay more attention to

other particularities of Turabian style in the writing process differently than the APA style. These particularities include, among other things, writing numbers, quoting the author's message, paging/page format, writing headings, endnotes/footnotes, (and so on). For example, when I was reading materials containing citations to other works, I could not confidently figure out whether I had to cite that other source to which the material had referred. This coursepack gave me the confidence to ignore that other citation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 48). At the same time, the Chicago style allows me to emphasize the quote or insist on material information or correct errors found in the original passage without changing the initial context of the author.

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In cases where I need to highlight particular words, notes, and translate words or phrases that are new to the reader, or if I want to emphasize them, I must italicize them or write them in quotation marks (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 47). The writing font is significant in CMS; it requires writing in Times New Roman, 12 (10 for footnotes), 1.5 indents for paragraphs, headings, references, and block quotes (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 49). Often, the writer may quote by omitting some parts of the passage by respecting the writing format. In this regard, permitting changes to quotations help the writer keep the passage's originality and structure while indicating what has been changed from the original quote when it is merged with their text. In this respect, I mainly understood the importance of the use of single and double quotation marks (" "), brackets [], ellipsis (...) to edit quotes. On this point, I learned that I could not use an ellipsis (...) unless, if some parts of the sentence are deleted, the sentence would be incomplete (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 49). In my undergraduate level, I learned to use *op.cit.*, *id.*, and *ibid* to avoid repeating the source I had used previously.

On the contrary, this coursepack warned me that these Latin abbreviations confuse readers who might not have memorized the source cited previously. Instead, if the bibliography is fully added to the paper, it allows the reader to find the source readily (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 51). The same applies when more than one author has discussed any material, the CMS style requires to cite all these sources/authors in references/endnotes. On the other hand, when the same author had discussed the same topic in different works, the CMS style requires that it be cited alike (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 53).

7) USE OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I studied law in the French system at my undergraduate level, mainly based on civil law. Looking at origin and legal development, I noticed the inevitable influence of the Latin language on the permitted development. In that context, legal courses emphasized Latin expressions for technical legal concepts. In our regular communication system, be it in English or French, we inevitably use some Latin abbreviations and expressions technically. Often, we do not pay much attention to their origin, meaning, rules, and exceptions for their use. In this context, I realize that these words have become famous for use in the academic field and daily life. These include, among many others, expressions to tell time (for example, P.M, A.M), abbreviations for page/pages (p., pp.), abbreviations and expressions to describe one's working experience (C.V./ Curriculum Vitae), (and so on).

Before starting this coursepack, I was among many lawyers who use Latin words or phrases in legal writing. Honestly, when using Latin words or phrases in legal writing, it was thought to impress the reader or be innovative. On the contrary, according to EUCLID, the writer should use clear language, avoid archaic words because they are strange to the readers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14). In addition, they cause the writer to make grammatical errors, and more importantly, they do not add any value to the intended message. EUCLID requires using the English equivalent of these abbreviations in business, formal, and technical writing to avoid misinterpretation by the reader and use plain English, which is simple, direct, clear, and understandable on the first reading (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 56). From this rule, I understand that Latin expressions can only be used if they are not equivalent in the English language.

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Many use these Latin abbreviations and expressions in our daily life without being fully knowledgeable of their exact meaning. EUCLID had dressed a list of these abbreviations and expressions and their equivalent English in this coursepack (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 56–61). I have been using abbreviations and terms in my academic and daily life. (For example, I use C.V. (*curriculum vitae*) when applying for a job. Suppose I cite a book that has more than one author. In that case, I must replace the rest of the authors by "*et al.*" (*et al. ii/aliae/Alia*). When expressing that Arsenal is playing against Chelsea, I use the abbreviation "VS." (*versus*). When giving an example to support or clarify an idea, I use, *e.g.* (*exempli gratia*), and many other abbreviations and expressions on the list of this coursepack. I used the abbreviation *et al.* without minding its gender distinction or plural vs. singular. My essential take home is that if I opt for using the abbreviation, *e.g.*, I must write the information in parentheses, which is different than I was previously using it.

8) SOME INCONSISTENCIES IN THE MATERIAL

As clarified on the page (ii) of the coursepack ACA-401D, period one (1), some mistakes in sample quotations or papers were intentionally not corrected in line with the need to teach and make the students figure out the errors. However, in addition to these necessary teaching examples, I found the following typos in the course material:

- Chapter two of the coursepack, "why mention the source?" the first sentence reads, "Why should anyone bother mentioning the source of where the information they are writing about
- Came from? What's the harm?".

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When reading the first sentence, I can see that it is incomplete; bullets had cut it, the second bullet should be the second part of the first sentence (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5). In addition, the coursepack warns the students to use contractions in their writing. However, the same sentence had used contraction (What's the harm?), unless it was intentionally used. On page 12, the coursepack mentions, "The basic rule you can use is that if it is repeated in many different sources that have you read, then you can assume it is common knowledge." This sentence uses an unnecessary subject reverse which should generally be used in a question, harmful or other indirect forms. On the same page, the

previous sentence: "what if you are new to a subject and you are researching a topic that you do not know, and you do not know if its common knowledge that can easily be found in numerous places?" Chapter four of the coursepack on literature review details the proper uses of "its" and "it is." This point regulates that "its" is used for possessive forms (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 18). In this sentence highlighted on page 12, I realize that "its" was wrongly used because the writer intended to use "it's" as a contraction of "it is."

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9) CONCLUSION

This course, together with the supplementary video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, came at the right time because it provided me the tips and practical guidance on how to effectively write my academic papers, as well as other work-related documents. EUCLID had done academic research and wrote a critical learning process. It is at the same time the learning-by-doing method that EUCLID had created to enable its students to accomplish the scientific works required to complete their programs. This course has not only given me fundamental guidance for effective academic writing needed at the early beginning of the program, but it has also been a tool to strengthen my English use in daily personal and professional life. The coursepack did not teach me to be effective in format and structure of the writings only, but also how to effectively arrange my ideas from a simple concept to evidence production, how to present my arguments clearly and constructively, and significantly recognize other people's efforts and time invested in their works by observing anti-plagiarism rules. It is invaluable for me to start the DMCR program at the EUCLID with this course. Therefore, I am confident that I will be writing my academic papers effectively. In doing so, I will have this course material in front of me and be consulting it as much as possible because I cannot assume to have memorized all the rules encompassed in it. However, as it is a learn-by-doing tool, and that practice makes things better, given that I will have to write many different papers, the more I will be applying them in my writings, the more I will master every single rule.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd Ed. Bangui: Euclid University.
- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.